

**Digital women and entrepreneurship in the social media
study on a sample of e-women marketers in Bechar**

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ABSTRACT

Since the 1990s, Algeria has embraced a market economy with the information technology revolution to develop small businesses for young people. An example, the Algerian woman who was able to exploit social networking sites for e-marketing, and to achieve entrepreneurship and business management in her home. The research paper explains the advantages of social media marketing, an explanation of the e-marketing process and how Algerian women have benefited from it. The researcher relied on the descriptive analytical method, and the electronic questionnaire tool to help study on virtual community. One of the most important results that we reached is that e-work has controls and rules that women must adhere to, and that the woman working through Facebook does not move to the center or office of work, and this work enables them to satisfy a large part of their personal or family needs. Thus, it develops entrepreneurship for women as a small institution in her home and it stimulates the movement of the economy in the country.

**Les femmes numériques et l'entrepreneuriat aux social media
étude sur un échantillon de femmes commerçantes électroniques à Bechar**

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RÉSUMÉ

Depuis les années 1990, l'Algérie a adopté une économie de marché avec la révolution des technologies de l'information pour développer les petites entreprises pour les jeunes. Un exemple, la femme algérienne qui a pu exploiter des sites de réseautage social pour l'e-marketing et réaliser l'entrepreneuriat et la gestion d'entreprise chez elle. Le document de recherche explique les avantages du marketing des médias sociaux, une explication du processus de marketing électronique et comment les femmes algériennes en ont bénéficié. Le chercheur s'est appuyé sur la méthode analytique descriptive et l'outil de questionnaire électronique pour aider à étudier la communauté virtuelle. L'un des résultats les plus importants que nous ayons atteints est que le travail électronique comporte des contrôles et des règles auxquels les femmes doivent se conformer, et que la femme travaillant via Facebook ne se déplace pas vers le centre ou le bureau de travail, et ce travail leur permet de satisfaire une grande partie de leurs besoins personnels ou familiaux. Ainsi, il développe l'entrepreneuriat pour les femmes en tant que petite institution dans sa maison et il stimule le mouvement de l'économie dans le pays.

- **INTRODUCTION**

Social media has become more prosperous than traditional media because of its importance as it provides a forum for discussion, spreading ideas and innovations, and exchanging experiences and experiences.

This technology can be used in the face of women's unemployment and empowerment in public affairs, which is beneficial to the nation's economy and improving productivity, which is a useful system, especially in the market economy and the development of industries and entrepreneurship on the productive level.

Teleworking is defined as an existing system of work located far from the employment office, production sites, or enterprise. So, the worker is separate from personal contact with other workers and employers, modern technology facilitates the worker's separation from the official job site by achieving what is called decentralization.

This good option has helped women in adopting projects such as food and textiles manufacturing, home nursery services, computer software production, consulting, electronic activities, and marketing of various household products and cosmetics ... through social media networks that are done directly to the consumer or through the mediator .

Through the research paper, we try to poll the workers' views remotely in Algeria about the extent of their use of social media applications to launch their products and exploit electronic marketing to improve women's production and enable them to integrate into public affairs and support the economic and contracting sector.

The study was divided into two main approaches:

Axis for social media and electronic marketing

1- Marketing via social media

2- The advantages of social media marketing

And Axis for women and electronic work

1- Women's electronic work, the positive and the negative side

2- The digital experience of Algerian women in electronic work

And we made the applied side to monitor women's experiences in electronic work using the social network Facebook for the purpose of marketing local clothing, accessories and cosmetics.

- **THE PROBLEMATIC:**

With the recent technological development and the rapid spread of communication technology and networks, the so-called electronic work system has emerged in order to give an opportunity to Algerian women in accordance with their circumstances.

Perhaps the emergence of the second generation of the Internet, or what is known as the Web 2.0, has provided more opportunities to bring about this communication and communication through social networking sites that also enabled users to post and share instead of browsing.

The spread of social networks has made many operating companies, entrepreneurs and projects participate in it thanks to the large and diverse society and the rapid spread of information in the virtual space, in order to present various activities, programs and marketing plans.

Women benefit from electronic work through the definition and promotion of their goods because customers are found in many social media networks. From this, the central question can be asked as follows:

How did the media help digital women in the field of electronic commerce? How does social media contribute to facilitating the electronic work of Algerian women, and how can entrepreneurship be achieved by new media?

- **OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:**

The importance of the study is that it sheds light on the advantages of the media in empowering women economically through developing their capabilities and honing their creativity in electronic marketing as a new direction for women's electronic work. Also, trying to identify the benefits of electronic work and the obstacles that a woman faces while she is working in her home through social networks and not moving to a place to work.

For this purpose, the study aims to research the possibility of exploiting modern technologies in the marketing function and show the importance of using social media in the current era and the resulting positive benefits that serve women and take care of their concerns and respond to their requirements.

- **THE SAMPLE IN OF STUDY:**

We distributed the electronic questionnaire to a sample of the electronics marketers on the network, and they were reached by participating in electronic marketing groups (for clothing sales, cosmetics, and accessories..)

Since the research community is a forked digital, characterized by intensity, magnitude, and heterogeneity, it was difficult to control it. We were satisfied with 100 individuals who answered the questionnaire, using the method of the **Accidental Sample** to represent the community correctly. In other words, a study of the number of respondents who answered the questionnaire during its presentation on the social networking site.

- **PROCEDURAL CONCEPTS:**

1- Social Media:

Social media is harnessing web applications and websites to create fast and more effective communication links. Social media has provided many opportunities, including sharing information between all users of the network with the capabilities of direct and free interaction on social sites.

Andreas Kaplan and Michael Hanlin defined social media as a set of Internet applications built on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2, which were characterized by the creation and exchange of user-generated content.

2- Digital Woman: Digital Woman

She is the networked woman who is interested in computing, information and communication technology, and by entering the field of digital integration and the era of digital media, she has managed to create for her a kind of independence in work and productivity and has benefited from digitization through e-marketing.

3- Teleworking (e-work)

The problems of transportation in the major industrial cities resulted in corn times to establish a telecommuting system to get rid of road congestion, and to carry out work in its time until this system was called telework and those working in it by remote workers or deputy workers, Remote Workers, and Teleworking is performing tasks from a place separate from the main offices or traditional places to do work, and it uses electronic means of communication to be able to maintain contact with the employer or the organization's main center.

4- Electronic Marketing: e-marketing

Also known as digital marketing or web marketing, it includes all transactions and practices using the internet-related means and digital technology by identifying and activating the demand for goods and services according to an objective plan and strategy. It takes into account setting a price for the products to be marketed, how to promote them and creating new ideas and methods for distributing them in order to achieve the goals of consumers.

- **SOCIAL MEDIA AND E-MARKETING:**

Technology changes have driven business, entrepreneurship and marketing, which is one of the most important of the World Wide Web, which resulted in many concepts, such as Internet marketing, but with the succession of developments on this network, social media or social networks have emerged, which has been widely popular by individuals.

Which led the institutions to resort through these networks, to market their products and services to the largest number of individuals and try to communicate and interact with them, and thus the concept of marketing through social networking sites which considered the famous French writer Lendrevie considered the marketing of the era.

1 / Social media marketing:

Marketing via websites or social networks has been defined as the use of social networks, blogs and wikis for the purpose of marketing, selling, public relations or customer service, these tools allow customers to interact with commercial companies, as well as organizations can open channels of communication with these customers and communicate with them in an interactive manner.

Thus, social media allows the development of corporate marketing functions, and becomes a means of interaction between them and the customer community in order to take advantage of their advantages and the ability to identify the behavior of each customer and enhance the relationship with him.

Facebook is the largest popular and most intense among users, which led marketing men to seize this network and consider it a marketing opportunity for their customers and direct their marketing programs and advertising campaigns to these networks, especially as it allows them to track customers and better understand their ideas and feelings, deal with complaints efficiently and improve public participation .

Also, Facebook pages are much more detailed than Twitter and Instagram accounts, since they allow advertisers to post any amount of information about their products and add videos and photos without certain limits. Also, using Facebook in marketing is very easy to choose the customer, how to target it, and the way to access it from By identifying who are the targets, what are their ages and geographical locations.

The process of social media marketing is illustrated through the form presented by the studies office of Forrest International, and we explain it as follows:

The four stages of a social media marketing strategy:

People are the target audience of the company, which they must know, through their personal files, their interests and needs, that is, they are the core of social sites.

Objectives intended to define the objectives of the marketing plan, by ensuring that it is compatible with the customer to provide better services to him.

Strategy The strategy is determined by getting close to the audience and recording its admiration and participation in order to draw up a plan that controls how and how it can be implemented.

Technology is the type of platform chosen to implement the plan, such as Blogger, Wiki, Twitter, Instagram, Facebook ...

2/ Advantages of social media marketing:

Marketing achieves economic growth and prosperity, and by relying on an effective marketing system in any country that raises the volume of trade exchange with client countries, including the introduction of hard currency, which increases economic development and prosperity.

Then, an online marketing activity parallel to traditional high-efficiency marketing allows the opening of new markets and the delivery of the commodity to the consumer at the right place and time.

Social media has a great role in facilitating exchanges in Algeria and making them more practical, whether in public or private institutions. For the free marketers, social networks especially Facebook and Twitter, which are most used in Algeria, have opened a wide field in front of displaying their products to the largest customers, especially The tremendous spread of the use of social media applications in smartphones and electronic boards so that the product or service is easy to access and know anywhere and at any time the customer wants, and the advantages of marketing via social networks are as stated in the Marketing book for the French Lendrevie, briefed into three advantages:

- The customer receives advertising messages, so that he is fully aware of the products and services of the economic establishment or the free marketers and all that is presented in the social networking market, and can also review the comments and criticisms about the product, which enables him to form a mental image and make decisions.
- The customer speaks and expresses his opinion about the product, through suggestions and criticisms or expresses satisfaction with the product, and this is what the institution or the marketer can benefit from from developing or improving its products. In social networks, the customer becomes an active partner in the market and in Promoting services and commodities to marketers.
- The customer fears in the marketer, as the advantage of receiving and expressing opinion with respect to the customer earns the latter met the marketer, as social media as a new method in marketing achieves what is called the impact of the source, as a psychological factor that affects the consumer, as the customer is on the communication pages Social is interested in authorized comments about the product, and this is what leads to the establishment or change of its buying behavior.

In addition to some of the advantages that are calculated on marketing via social networks for the benefit of large companies and institutions based on defamation of their trademarks and gaining the largest percentage of dealers, and the process of rapid and direct access to them, and the emergence of competitiveness by improving the image through the large gatherings of consumers, so Marketers should choose the quick-profit method with minimal effort.

- **WOMEN WORK ONLINE .. LEGAL GAIN AND A SAFE ENVIRONMENT**

The great development in information and communication technology and the emergence of the rapidly evolving information and technology revolution have brought about a change in working methods, and the remote work method is only one of the methods that began to invade the business sectors in a growing and noticeable way.

As a result of this progress, the number of organizations that choose to keep their workers in their homes, perhaps in another city or even another country, increases every day due to the many advantages that can result from this method in many cases and that do not depend on reducing costs only (due to the lack of need To office space and other costs like transportation).

It is useful in the case of working women who want to combine work and care for their families.

Below we try to present the concept of remote work and some of its pros and cons, and how Algerian women benefited from it.

1/ Online work pros and cons:

With the emergence of the idea of working remotely in the United States of America at first, I was limited to working from home using modern means of communication to expand and include work anywhere and not only at home, people began to perform their duties and jobs in hotels, cars and private centers for remote work, whether Created by companies or local communities, where work can be done remotely anywhere the electronic networks are available, whether wired or wireless.

And it includes some employees performing all or part of the work duties in their homes through direct contact with their management in the company through the Internet, and of course this system is limited to businesses that use the computer or that do not require an actual direct partnership in performance with others.

However, working at home requires several arrangements, the most important of which is to allocate a special place to work at home, to preserve work documents and the confidentiality they may require, focus on its completion, and provide the workplace with modern means of communication and the equipment it needs to accomplish.

Also, success in doing work at home requires allocating times for work that do not interfere with personal, family or social activities, even if they are in a degree of flexibility, so that the work does not become a secondary activity dominated by preoccupation with other living matters.

The woman was the most benefiting from that system, as it allowed her to combine the performance of her homework and family duties, and care for her family without conflict with her work duties, and without psychological, nervous and physical pressures. It is no longer difficult to combine work, family affairs and caring for the family, as working women are able to marry and have early childbearing, which prevented them and build a future in the field of work that guarantees them a material resource, in addition to achieving their ambitions or achieving themselves, as well as This system has benefited companies to reduce office spending and expansion while increasing production and reducing outages.

One of the good things about working remotely is that everyone can benefit from it, and women can benefit from it by:

- Satisfy and enrich her needs
- Exploiting leisure time to benefit it
- Compensating money, the woman does not need to buy clothes and tools to go out every morning to work, and to avoid road noise and transportation costs.
- Psychological and physical comfort, so it does not have to overburden the home and overwork the outside work.
- Opening job opportunities for women with disabilities.

2/ Experience of the Algerian digital woman in electronic work:

Algerian women took advantage of this digital transformation and benefited from this new economic pattern. They entered the field of digital commerce through electronic shopping in various forms, and tried to provide themselves with a profit at the lowest costs and invest in their local products and activate their capabilities, and they relied on that on applications Social media introduces its authentic products and practices working with companies and organizations comfortably.

The idea of remote work was a western idea embraced by the United States and some European countries (Britain, Spain, Finland) and international experiences such as Japan and Canada, and even developing countries and Arab countries embraced the idea of working a woman from her home as a legitimate requirement. As God said, "Stay in your homes." The idea of "working remotely" came with various alternatives, the woman avoiding the problems related to her going out to work, mixing with men, and the hardship of leaving her home, allowing her the opportunity to reconcile work and caring for her family, and ensuring her a decent life that guarantees She has the right to work in a legitimate work environment to contribute to the development of her community, in a manner that responds to her needs, and provides her with social and economic stability.

Although the Algerian woman's experience in the digital environment and entered the field of electronic commerce came late compared to her counterparts in the countries of the Middle East, the technological factors and technical

openness helped her to adopt work remotely through her home or in mobile places without the need for an official place to practice her job.

And the forms of Algerian women work appeared in their beginnings, limited to dealing with commercial agents and economic dealers, or their affiliation with major commercial centers through working as a sales distributor from her home or providing services via the Internet, such as working with Algerian telecom operators (Djezzy, Mobilis, Ooredoo ..) And some secretarial and administrative work, and even engaging in charities and calling on the line, or by promoting products in commercial branches of cosmetics, for example, Oriflame, or marketing of clothes, accessories, party supplies, and reservations by phone or network.

And with the development of the Facebook network and its spread throughout Algeria, the interest of Algerian women have shifted to their local production and marketing of their home products by introducing them through Facebook and Twitter, often, they have published special videos of their home crafts, such as sewing and embroidering, cooking and household measures, so, Facebook became full of live pictures of their achievements in order to earn profit and meet their daily needs, in terms of projects and small businesses.

I. ANALYZE AND DISCUSS THE RESULTS:

The age of the sample items of the Algerian marketers in the field of selling clothes and accessories varied by adopting Facebook between 18 to 25 years, by 62.5%, and those who increased from 26 to 35 years by about 20.8%, while the percentage of 16.6% who were over the age of 35, as a sample, varied between Maidens and married women of equal size are around 50%, with different levels of education.

Whereas, 33.5% of them have secondary education and 45.8% have a university degree.

FIGURE1: AGES AND EDUCATIONAL LEVEL OF THE STUDIED SAMPLE

This is evidence that electronic work through the use of social networking sites is not subject to age or social status changes, not even the level of education, as social media is available to all segments of society, and that the Facebook space is an open space for displaying goods and services to a large and wide audience of consumers and customers and even Competitors.

FIGURE2: TYPES OF ELECTRONIC WORK FOR ALGERIAN WOMEN

Most Algerian marketers for clothes and accessories state that they trade work from her home or anywhere, as long as they are connected to Facebook and can communicate with customers and dealers, as they represent 71.3% of the type of self-employment that depends on the marketing of handicrafts such as sewing, detailing and models, while the business of companies and Clothing store increased by 28.7%, This is because most of the respondents market their home craft freely and without the rules and conditions of employers.

As for the payment process adopted by the marketers via Facebook, most of them were the adoption of postal or bank transfers at a rate of 28.3% in the absence of a clear method of payment by credit card, due to the lack of availability at the level of customers, while workers working remotely from members of the sample to the payment process upon receipt as a method Guaranteed traditional to both parties.

Algerian women prefer Facebook marketing through smart phones because of their flexibility and process of use by 51.6%, then the laptop by 30.8%, and electronic boards by 17.5%.

TABLE1 : ELECTRONIC MEDIUM USED TO MARKET THE PRODUCT

Electronic medium	percentage %
Smartphone	51.6%
Laptop	30.8%
Electronic tablet	17.5%
Total	100 %

Electronics marketers state their resort to remote work and the adoption of Facebook as a site to promote their products to:

- Reaching a large group of people regardless of the number and wherever they are by 62%
- Addressing the buyer more personally and individually to attract and attract him 35% better.
- Reducing costs, saving transportation and shortening time, increasing productivity and improving its quality by 14%
- Facing unemployment and fulfilling my material and moral needs by 9%.

While they face several difficulties, they were represented in the following:

- Difficulty delivering the goods to the customer
- Lack of after-sales services such as returning or replacing the commodity
- Some buyers are afraid of selling through the site
- The necessity of having an electronic medium which could generate and produce countless technical and communication problems.

II. CONCLUSION

Marketing via social media is considered one of the most important methods and strategies for marketing recently popular, as it is based on the use of different social networks as a platform for the application of various marketing programs and plans, as these networks attract a huge amount of individuals and groups from different circles and varieties who are considered an attractive market for companies and institutions And among the most important of these networks are Facebook, Twitter, Google Plus, YouTube ... etc, and the media will thus provide women with job opportunities, gain profits, achieve profitability and entrepreneurship, and hence the growth of the country's economy.

This means that there is a great relationship between small institutions (women in their homes), the media, and the national economy.

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